

Representation of Semantic Encoding in Low and Intermediate Level Visual Regions

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Abstract

Understanding how the visual system processes and categorizes objects is a fundamental question in neuroscience. This study investigated whether early visual areas encode semantic category information independently of low-level visual features. Using fMRI data from the Kay Natural Images dataset, we focused on V1–V4 and LOC. We explored three binary distinctions: animate vs. inanimate, natural vs. human-made, and face-present vs face-absent. We also included an extended face category encompassing partial and animal faces. To address these questions, we used Representational Similarity Analysis (RSA) and controlled for low-level structure with features from AlexNet's Conv2 layer. Our results revealed that both animacy and the extended face category are represented across early, intermediate, and higher visual areas, independent of low-level visual features. Significant encoding emerged in V2–V4 and LOC, highlighting an early prioritization of evolutionarily relevant information within the visual system.

Introduction

The ability to rapidly categorize objects is a cornerstone of visual perception and cognition, enabling us to interact with the world efficiently. A long-standing debate within the field of visual neuroscience centers on the neural locus of semantic category representations. Some theories propose that these representations are primarily localized in higher-level cognitive areas, such as the prefrontal cortex (Freedman et al., 2001), while others suggest that categorical information may emerge earlier in the visual processing stream (Long, Yu, & Konkle, 2018).

While early visual areas like V1 are well-known for their sensitivity to basic visual features such as orientation, spatial frequency, and contrast (Hubel & Wiesel, 1962; Riesenhuber & Poggio, 1999), the extent to which these areas also encode broader semantic categories remains uncertain. Specifically, do categories like animate/inanimate, natural/human-made, or face-present/face-absent simply represent a byproduct of processing low-level features, or do they reflect neural computations related to the specific categories? This distinction is critical for understanding the hierarchical organization of the visual system and the mechanisms by which the brain transforms basic sensory input into meaningful object representations.

This study aims to address this question by investigating the encoding of our four categorical distinctions in early and intermediate visual areas, while explicitly controlling for the contribution of low-level feature representations. We hypothesize that if category-specific information is present beyond what can be explained by low-level features, it would provide evidence for the emergence of categorical representations within the early and intermediate levels of the visual system.

Methods

Using the fMRI dataset from Kay et al. (2008), we focused on early and intermediate visual areas (V1–V4) and lateral occipital cortex (LOC) while participants viewed natural images. Additionally, we asked three independent raters to label images as animate or inanimate, natural or human-made, Strict face-present or absent category, which is only positive when human faces are present in the image, and finally, the comprehensive face-present vs face-absent category, which also included partial and animal faces. Images deemed "ambiguous" were removed, leaving 1695 images for the animate/inanimate analysis, 1693 for natural/human-made, and 1750 for face-present versus face-absent.

We calculated a neural representational dissimilarity matrix (RDM) for each region of interest (ROI) by computing Euclidean distances between voxel-wise response patterns. We then compared these neural RDMs with the categorical model RDMs (see Figure 1, Panel A). To capture low-level visual structure, we extracted features from the second convolutional layer of AlexNet, whose earliest layers converge on Gabor-like filters, and computed a low-level RDM from these feature distances (Krizhevsky, Sutskever, & Hinton, 2012). This step allowed us to account for low-level information in the stimulus set.

We gauged category signals by correlating each ROI's neural RDM with the corresponding categorical model RDMs. To dissociate semantic effects from the influence of low-level visual features, we used multivariate distance matrix regression (MDMR) (Zapala & Schork, 2006). In

this approach, each category RDM was entered as a predictor alongside the low-level RDM to determine whether it explained additional variance in the neural responses

In addition to MDMR, we conducted variance partitioning analyses to isolate each categorical model's unique contribution beyond low-level visual properties and implemented Support vector machines (SVM) classification with stratified 5-fold cross-validation to predict categorical labels from standardized voxel responses, evaluating performance through Receiver-operating characteristic (ROC) curves and Area under the curve (AUC) discriminability indices.

Results

We investigated the representation of four semantic distinctions, defined by the model Representational Dissimilarity Matrices (RDMs) shown in Figure 1A, across visual ROIs (V1-V4, LOC). We assessed unique semantic encoding using partial Multivariate Distance Matrix Regression (MDMR) and variance partitioning, controlling for low-level visual features (AlexNet Conv2 RDM) and evaluated classification performance using SVMs.

Animate versus Inanimate

Zero-order representational-similarity analysis revealed that neural dissimilarity matrices became increasingly aligned with the animacy model, rising from negligible Kendall's τ scores in V1 to significant values in LOC (Figure 1, Panel B, upper-left). When low-level image structure accounted for, the partial MDMR F statistic showed no unique animacy coding in V1 ($F = 0.48$, $p = .51$) but an apparent, monotonic increase through V2 ($F = 0.68$, $p = .027$) to a peak in LOC ($F = 5.04$, $p < .001$; Figure 1, Panel C, upper-left). This sharpening in values indicates a growing population of voxels whose distances are uniquely explained by animacy after controlling for

AlexNet-Conv2 features. Consistent with the representational data, single-image decoding rose from chance level in V1 to moderate accuracy in V2–V3 and reached a near-ceiling AUC of 0.885 in LOC (Figure 1, Panel E, upper-left).

Comprehensive Face-Present vs Face-Absent.

Neural similarity became strongly face-aligned as we continued along the visual hierarchy, with Kendall's τ correlation values climbing from V1 to LOC (Figure 1, Panel B, upper-right). The partial MDMR F-values also demonstrated a similar gradient: V1 was non-significant ($F = 0.53$, $p = .24$), but V2 already showed strong signs of category encoding ($F = 0.69$, $p < 0.05$), and LOC exhibited a pronounced F-Value of 3.29 ($p < .001$; Figure 1, Panel C, upper-right).

Correspondingly, ROC curves improved from an AUC of 0.585 in V2 to 0.861 in LOC, underscoring the high decodability of broadly defined face cues (Figure 1, Panel E, upper-right).

Strict Face-Present vs. Face Absent

Using a strictly human-face definition produced weaker effects. Kendall's τ values were lower than for the extended contrast yet increased toward LOC (Figure 1, Panel B, lower-left). Partial MDMR first reached significance in V4 ($F = 0.67$, $p < .05$) and peaked in LOC ($F = 0.79$, $p < .001$; Figure 1, Panel C, lower-left). Decoding accuracy followed suit with lower AUC values across the visual hierarchy compared to the comprehensive Face-Present vs. Absent and Animate vs. Inanimate categories (Figure 1, Panel E, lower-left).

Natural versus Human-Made

Kendall's τ correlations for the natural–human-made model were modest and showed no systematic increase across ROIs (Figure 1, Panel B, lower-right). After the low-level structure

was accounted for, partial MDMR revealed minimal unique variance in every region, with F values ranging from 0.39 to 0.65 and with all having p values >0.05 after FDR correction (Figure 1, Panel C, lower-right). Similarly, classification analyses showed significantly lower AUC scores all across the hierarchy compared to animacy and comprehensive face distinctions (Figure 1, Panel E, lower-right).

Figure 1. Multi-method evaluation of semantic-category information in early and intermediate visual cortex (ROIs = V1–V4 and lateral occipital cortex, LOC).

A. Representational Dissimilarity Matrices for Animate vs. Inanimate, Comprehensive Face-present vs. Face-absent, Human Face-present vs Face-absent, and Human-made vs Natural. Warm colors (red) indicate large dissimilarity between classes for that stimulus; cool colors (blue) indicate low dissimilarity within a class.

B. Bars show Kendall's τ correlations between the neural RDM of each ROI and the matching categorical RDM (mean across participants). Significance after FDR correction is marked by asterisks (*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$).

C. Multivariate distance-matrix regression was run while partialling out AlexNet-conv2 features. Blue bars indicate F statistics quantifying variance uniquely explained by the semantic model; red bars = associated FDR-corrected p-values.

D. Left bar plots give mean ΔR^2 —the increase in explained variance when the categorical model is added on top of low-level predictors—for each ROI. Right violin plots display the full voxel-wise distribution of ΔR^2 .

E. ROC curves from SVMs trained within each ROI for the four binary classifications. Colored lines correspond to different ROIs.

Discussion

Our results highlight that a significant portion of the variance in the early visual cortex is attributed to low-level feature tuning, although certain categories, particularly those with strong ecological or behavioral salience, exhibit unique encoding over such features. Among the categories we tested, Comprehensive face-present vs. face-absent and animacy clearly stood out. After controlling for low-level information, the presence of faces and animate stimuli had higher correlations with their respective categorical models, explained a meaningful portion of response variance in V2 to V4 and LOC when low-level features were controlled for, and were more easily decoded and classified across the visual hierarchy. These findings are consistent with the idea that face processing and animacy decoding are high-priority functions that can recruit multiple levels of the visual hierarchy earlier or more strongly than generic object categories might (Grill-Spector & Weiner, 2014).

Overall, these findings align with more interactive or recurrent models of visual processing (Lamme & Roelfsema, 2000; Bar, 2003; Gilbert & Li, 2013; Cichy et al., 2014). Such models propose that top-down and lateral connections enhance or modulate category signals even within

regions traditionally labeled as early or mid-level, leading to partial category selectivity below the high-level temporal areas. Our results thus support a hierarchical gradient: strong low-level dependence in V1, with progressively more category tuning in V2-V4 and beyond, especially for stimuli with high evolutionary or social significance, such as face presence and animacy.

Data and Code Availability

The fMRI data used in this study are publicly available from the Kay et al. (2008) publication. The code developed for analyses mentioned in the paper is publicly available on GitHub at https://github.com/UYildiz12/IS_Semcat.

References

- Bar, M. (2003). A cortical mechanism for triggering top-down facilitation in visual object recognition. *Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience*, 15(4), 600–609. <https://doi.org/10.1162/089892903321662976>
- Cichy, R. M., Pantazis, D., & Oliva, A. (2014). Resolving human object recognition in space and time. *Nature Neuroscience*, 17(3), 455–462. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.3635>
- Freedman, D. J., Riesenhuber, M., Poggio, T., & Miller, E. K. (2001). Categorical representation of visual stimuli in the primate prefrontal cortex. *Science*, 291(5502), 312–316.
- Gilbert, C. D., & Li, W. (2013). Top-down influences on visual processing. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 14(5), 350–363. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3464>
- Grill-Spector, K., & Weiner, K. S. (2014). The functional architecture of the ventral temporal cortex and its role in categorization. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 15(8), 536–548.

- Hubel, D. H., & Wiesel, T. N. (1962). Receptive fields, binocular interaction and functional architecture in the cat's visual cortex. *Journal of Physiology*, 160(1), 106–154.
- Kay, K. N., Naselaris, T., Prenger, R. J., & Gallant, J. L. (2008). Identifying natural images from human brain activity. *Nature*, 452(7185), 352–355. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06713>
- Kriegeskorte, N., Mur, M., & Bandettini, P. (2008). Representational similarity analysis—connecting the branches of systems neuroscience. *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience*, 2, Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/neuro.06.004.2008>
- Lamme, V. A. F., & Roelfsema, P. R. (2000). The distinct modes of vision offered by feedforward and recurrent processing. *Trends in Neurosciences*, 23(11), 571–579. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2236\(00\)01657-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2236(00)01657-X)
- Long, B., Yu, C. P., & Konkle, T. (2018). Mid-level visual features underlie the high-level categorical organization of the ventral stream. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(38), E9015–E9024.
- Riesenhuber, M., & Poggio, T. (1999). Hierarchical models of object recognition in cortex. *Nature Neuroscience*, 2(11), 1019–1025. <https://doi.org/10.1038/14819>
- Zapala, M. A. & Schork, N. J. (2006). Multivariate regression analysis of distance matrices for testing associations between gene expression patterns and related variables. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 103(51), 19430–19435.